

Transaction Application Program

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Abstract:- In receivables, creating a transaction for customer billing and which has the payment due date and accordingly customer makes the payment based on payment due date, after receiving the payment in bank statement, cash application team creates the receipt and applies on transaction, but still there is remaining amount exists since, TDS amount is deducted by the customer and makes the payment, Due to this, AR team knock off the remaining amount by creating credit memo and applies on transaction. Currently this activity performs manually, it can be handled when we have few credit memos. If volume is high, it will take time to complete the activity. We recommend here to develop a program where system applies the credit memos automatically as per date provided in flat file.

I. INTRODUCTION

The program will be used in receivables module to perform the application automatically for transactions. Program can be used at global level.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

When there are few transactions exists then it can be handled manually, whereas there is a high volume of transaction, it will take very time to complete the activity. On average of 100 CM to apply on transactions it will take 3-4 hours, in a month there will be 500+ CM's being created and all these to be applied, it takes approx. 15-20 hours spending time by team to do it manually

III. DESIGN OVERVIEW

Here we recommend solution to develop a program where system applies the credit memos on transaction automatically as per custom logic. Upload program loads the data into staging table and application program performs the application for transactions (Fig:1)

Fig. 1: Process flow

A. Data Requirement:

Transactions Details:

- Transaction Number
- Customer Number
- Transaction Date
- GL Date
- Apply Date
- Amount

B. Credit Memo Details:

- Credit Memo Number
- Transaction Date
- GL Date
- Amount

Development involves creating programs, directory to place the file and maintain staging table.

There are two programs to be developed as follows...

- AR CM Application Loader program
- AR CM Application Program

C. Directory:

Create a directory folder (FTP) to upload the flat file to import data into staging table to validate and process.

➤ Staging Table:

Once we upload the file into FTP folder, program get's triggered and data will get inserted into staging table to process, we need to create a staging table needs for data insertion. Ensure that all the required columns to be created for validation so that data can be processed.

D. Create a Flat File:

Create a flat file, it can be in .csv format, 'comma' delimited and provide with all necessary columns such as transaction number, customer number, GL date, transaction,

Fig. 3: Application Window

IV. OUTCOME

After submitting the programs loader program and application program, system does the application automatically without having manual intervention (Fig.4)

Fig. 4: Chart showing about efforts between manual and automation

V. CONCLUSION

- **Benefit:** As discussed with business, approx. 100 CMs to apply against transactions it will take around 3-4 hours, In a moth there will be 500+ CM's so overall time taken in a month to perform this activity manually around 15-20 hours If we use the program, system will take 10-15 mins approximately for 100 CM's, likewise the program can be used at global level i.e., all other entities also can use it and impact will be high. Especially during month end times helps a lot for effective closure.

- **User Errors:** We can reduce human error since program does the activity
- **Productivity:** User productivity will be increased, so that user can focus on other activities

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